

CONTEMPORARY IMPROVEMENTS IN MODERN EDUCATION OF UZBEKISTAN

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ABSTRACT

This article studies the system of higher education of the Republic of Uzbekistan. The author examines the issues of reforming higher education in the context of deepening democratic reforms in a new stage of the country's development. The paper studies topical issues of improving the activities of higher educational institutions. An attempt was made to study the current state of higher education and the most important strategic tasks facing it, which directly affect the methods, content, and also the creation of an intellectual environment for future bachelors and masters.

Keywords: higher education, sector, innovation, integrated into the system.

Higher education institutions have assumed a major role in the social and economic development of countries. Recently, there has been a transformation from the traditional to the modern within a new approach. In this dynamic environment, universities are not only responsible for teaching and research activities but are also responsible for responding to students' demands, the government, and the business world. As higher education environment has changed mainly because of globalization and a number of other relevant international trends, understanding all these trends is a very significant factor for the improvement of universities. During the transformation process, universities should be aware of all new approaches in the higher education area to prepare their students for a new world. Several individuals, newspapers, and magazines have mentioned the transformation process in the higher education sector, but have not comprehended it in depth. The purpose of this article is to underscore the determined trends and developments in higher education. First, the article reviews relevant literature. Then, it lists the eight approaches. The study uses the related literature as the basis to explain all eight identified developments and trends. The article concludes with a summary of the developments and trends to grasp the new approaches in the transformation process of higher education.

For disseminating knowledge, higher education institutions cannot function without new information technologies. Information technology assists educational

institutions to become more competitive within both the national and international contexts. In parallel with all changes in higher education, universities can be regarded as a commercial product, governed essentially by market forces, and has brought in the concept of competitiveness (Mohamedbhai, 2003). Universities have to compete for funding, innovation, collaborations, new technologies, research, and recruitment of students. Therefore, the higher education institutions need a new management approach.

The academic changes of the late 20th and early 21st centuries are more extensive due to their global nature and the number of institutions and people they affect, and in the early 21st century, higher education has become a competitive enterprise (Altbach et al., 2009).

If we turn to world practice, we will see that the general trends in the development of higher education today are - fundamentalization, pragmatization, computerization, individualization, humanization, standardization. At the same time, individual educational programs, external studies, distance learning are actually becoming a modern educational reality, where the production, storage, transmission and consumption of information take place with the help of computer and Internet technologies (Djavakova K. 2022).

In 2012, the professorship of Stanford University, a private research university in the United States, one of the most authoritative and ranked in the United States and in the world, publishes its lectures and launches the Coursera online platform. The initiative was taken up by the leading universities of the world. Currently, Coursera, the most popular platform, cooperates with 149 universities. Two American providers Udacity and edX and the European MOOC Initiative, the Association of Distance Universities in Europe, compete with this platform (Kasyanova L).

The end of the twentieth century marked a significant impact on social development of a number of global problems of mankind, the resolution of which can be interconnected with the tasks of the local character. The educational systems of each state must form a citizen of the world, successfully mastering the culture of peace. However, the development of global values should not interfere and counteract the mental, root characteristics of national systems of education and upbringing. Rather, globalization educational training will be the more significant, the stronger it is linked to the national-state tasks and principles of its implementation.

A particular interest to our study may be traced to the article by D. B. Johnstone, (2015) «Financing higher education: Worldwide perspectives and policy options». As the author argues, the diverging trajectories of very rapidly increasing resource needs and faltering revenues from state budgets have to be met by solutions on the cost side, or on the revenue side. The cost-revenue squeeze and the resulting institutional and

system austerity, as well as some of the so-called solutions to these dilemmas, can have deleterious impacts on the quality and capacity of universities and colleges(Johnstone, D. B. (2015).

With regard to the scope of coverage of the population by higher education, Uzbekistan has reached the level of the developed countries of the world. Such a high rate was achieved through the policy of open access and continuous education, which provides the opportunity to obtain higher education in the most favourable conditions. For instance, a significant consideration is given to evening and correspondence modes of education which allows to study in off-work hours. Universities are integrated into the system of continuous education through their centers of further training. Multiple professional and civic associations offer various educational programmes for adults.

Mankind needs ideals and moral values, the rise levels of spirituality and culture. The noblest task decides education, is associated with the awakening of each national-patriotic and international spirit up to the realization of a high degree of universality of the world(Lysenko V. T 1993).The composition and competence of bodies and institutions of educational policies are specific to each state. In the same time characteristic trend of today, common to all national education systems, was the departure of the state from direct education management. State authorities education in modern conditions are increasingly acting as buyers of educational services of educational institutions, and the functions educational authorities are increasingly moving out of the sphere production of educational services in the field of protection of interests consumers of services of educational institutions.

In improving the efficiency of the education process, a huge role belongs to information technology. Unfortunately need to state that today the level remains low the use of information technologies in the educational sphere as from the point of view of expanding access, and from the point of view of the use of new teaching methods. Measures taken to address these issues will promote the widespread use of ICT tools, will allow much more flexibility and lower costs to choose courses for training, master the content of the relevant specialties provided higher education.The introduction of modern educational programs, pedagogical and smart technologies in the educational process will help significant improvement in the quality of education. Obviously positive imprint on the quality training of highly qualified specialists will impose the organization of remote classes and seminars, videoconferencing, which will also contribute to strengthening interactive interaction and cooperation between educational institutions, including foreign.The goal is to make our education meet the global standards, introduce advanced foreign methods for assessing knowledge, which will a guarantee of the quality and efficiency of the education system Thus, new educational standards should become one of the most important means increasing the level of

training of specialists with higher education through mastering the basics of professional activity, methods, methods and skills of individual and collective performance of research work, development of abilities for scientific creativity, research independence and, as a result, the formation highly professional specialists capable of generating new knowledge and its effective application in the context of globalization.

In Uzbekistan has a great understanding that constant investment in called "human capital" and education are the key to formation of a developed democratic state, permanent engine of progress and an indispensable condition for the modernization direction of national development. As rightly noted by on this occasion, the President "... achieving the noble goals facing the people of Uzbekistan, the future of the country, its prosperity and well-being, then, what place it will take in the world community in the 21st century - it all depends, first of all, from the new generation, from what our children will grow up to be" This postulate has always received due support and recognition on state level, and moreover, day by day he grows stronger in the mind people, which creates a solid layer and foundation for a bright and great future

REFERENCES:

1. Mohamedbhai, G., (2003). Globalization and its implications for universities in developing countries. Universities and globalization: Private linkages, public trust. (pp. 153-162). In, G. Breton & M. Lambert (Eds.), Berlin: Walter de Gruyter GmbH & Co. KG.
2. Altbach, (2006). Globalization and the universities: And realities in an unequal world. In, F. James & G. Altbach (Eds.), International handbook of higher education (pp. 121-139). Springer
3. Djavakova K. (2022). Modern education and its quality: Development trends. Science and innovation international scientific journal volume 2 issue 3 MARCH 2023 UIF-2022: 8.2 | ISSN: 2181-3337 | SCIENTISTS.UZ.
4. Johnstone, D. B. (2015). Financing higher education: Worldwide perspectives and policy options. THF Working Paper: Working Papers Series, No. 6. Retrieved from [http://www.headfoundation.org/papers/_2015_65\)_Financing_H_Ed_WW_Perspectives_and_policy_options.pdf](http://www.headfoundation.org/papers/_2015_65)_Financing_H_Ed_WW_Perspectives_and_policy_options.pdf)
5. Kasyanova L. How the EU will build a digital educational space / L. Kasyanova [Electronic resource]. – Access mode: <http://cnews.ru/link / a3598>.
6. Lysenko V. The concept of global education // Public education. - 1993. -No. 7-8.